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Research Article

STUDY TO DETERMINE THE OUTCOME AND
COMPLICATIONS OF TOTAL HIP ARTHROPLASTY¹Dr. Ahmed Zohaib, ²Dr Faaiz Sultan, ³Dr Bilal Hassan¹ Arif Memorial Teaching Hospital, Lahore²Shalamar Hospital³Services Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Total hip arthroplasty is one of the furthest common key operating methods in orthopedics.**Objective:** The main objective of the study was to determine the results and complications of total hip arthroplasty.**Material and method:** All THA patients were involved in this forthcoming study. Patients with severe osteoarthritis of the psychiatric joints, bilateral osteoarthritis, knee, contraindications, history of arthroplasty for key surgery or lack of control support were excepted from the study. Harris Hip Score was used to assess hip fitness in the range of (poor-0) to (excellent-100). All patients were followed for 6 months. Facts was collected and analyzed using t-test analysis and SPSS.**Results:** Finally, 58 patients were evaluated; 24 of them (41.4%) are men and other women. The average age was 56.8 ± 16.56 . Post-operative complications include contamination (1 case), posterior hip disarticulation (2 cases) and peroneal nerve palsy (1 case). Mean of the preoperative HHS was 49.69 ± 5 , but increased expressively to 88.02 ± 4.04 six months after total hip replacement ($p < 0.001$).**Conclusion:** Giving to this control, total hip arthroplasty is related with marked enhancement and satisfactory result in patients, and the complication rate is low.**Key words:** orthopedics, Harris hip joint assessment, osteoarthritis.**Corresponding author:****Dr Ahmed Zohaib,**

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INTRODUCTION:

THA is an effective method for patients in the late stages of osteoarthritis. It can reduce pain, increase patients' walking ability and restore function. THA is one of the most common orthopedic surgeries and is widely practiced worldwide (over 1 million cases per year). Pain and dysfunction are the most common causes of THA due to degenerative changes in the hip joint¹⁻². Other indications for surgery are trauma, hip dislocation, avascular necrosis of the femoral neck, rheumatoid arthritis (RA), lupus, etc. According to previously published data, pain decreases after three to six months of THA and range of motion increases³.

The THA procedure can be associated with a number of complications such as infection, hip and knee pain, surgical site hematoma, ectopic ossification, thromboembolism, limb length discrepancies, prosthetic dislocation, and osteolysis⁴. These complications fall into three categories:

- 1) complications related to surgery in the operating room;
- 2) short-term complications after surgery;
- 3) late complications after surgery.

There aren't enough studies directly evaluating THA complications and results. The key determination of this study was to examine the results of THA in patients referring to hospitals in Pakistan. Our results will be helpful for clinicians to better investigate the positive and negative aspects of the THA procedure and to choose a good option for treating patients⁵.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study population: This prospective study was conducted in patients who were admitted for THA. Patients with severe knee osteoarthritis, history of arthroplasty, psychiatric disorder, bilateral osteoarthritis, major surgery contraindications and lack of follow-up were excluded from the study.

Data collection: The subsequent patient data was composed: sex, age, weight, height, occupation, family history, smoking history, underlying disease (including hip arthritis, diabetes, osteoporosis, etc.), history of hip fractures, type of fracture, surgical approach (back), postoperative complications (early relaxation, dislocation, wear, infection, nerve damage). Patients were evaluated in the third and sixth weeks of surgery and in the third and sixth

months after surgery. HHS was used to measure the physical performance of the hip. HHS is a scale that evaluates pain, patient function, deformation level, and hip range of motion during various activities. The score range of (90-100-excellent), (80-89-good), (70-79-average) and less than 70 weak.

Preoperative protocol: Surgical procedures and follow-up have been reported to the patients. After surgery, patients were assured of surgical care, pain relief and postoperative analgesia and discharge at home as soon as possible. Adequate antibiotic prophylaxis (intravenous Keflin 500 mg every 6 hours) was administered to all patients before surgery.

Surgical Procedure: All patients underwent THA by the same surgeon. The operations were performed with a posterolateral approach. The procedures take between 45 and 90 minutes. All implants had a standard cementless cup and a cementless stem.

Post-operative protocol: Thromboembolism prophylaxis (enoxaparin 4000 IU) was used in all patients until they walked independently. Enoxaparin was then replaced with aspirin (80 to 160 mg per day). Blood transfusions were given if necessary. Two days after surgery, patients were encouraged to walk (with a walker or walking stick) and physical therapy was started. They also took over the recycling activities of everyday life.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Composed data were analyzed by SPSS version 17.0. They underwent descriptive analysis. Also, t-test analysis was used to relate the HHS among different categories. A p-value less than 0.05 were measured statistically important.

Ethical issues: This study was approved by ethical committee and the study procedure was explained to all patients before surgery and the informed consent was obtained from all of them.

RESULTS:

A total of 58 patients, 24 patients (41.4%) men and 34 patients (58.6%) women were involved in this study. The mean age was 56.8 ± 16.56 . The salient features of the patients are shown in [Table/Figure-1].

[table/Fig-1]: Salient characteristics of the patients.	
Variable	N (%)
Gender	
Male	24 (41.4)
Female	34 (58.6)
age {Mean±SD (year)}	56.8±16.56
Smoking	
Yes	3 (5.2)
No	55 (94.8)
Opium intake	
Yes	6 (10.3)
No	52 (89.7)
Rheumatoid arthritis	
Yes	8 (13.8)
No	50 (86.2)
diabetes mellitus	
Yes	4 (6.9)
No	54 (93.1)

The indications for surgery are as follows: avascular necrosis of the femoral head, n = 20 (34.5%); hip dislocation, n = 17 (29.3%); degenerative joint disease, n = 16 (27.6%); femur-o-acetabular impingement, n = 5 (8.6%).

As for THA complications, postoperative infection was only observed in a male patient who appeared ten days after surgery. The complication was resolved with a seven-day course of antibiotics. Two patients older than 70 years (one male and one female) had postoperative posterior dislocation three months after surgery and this decreased in the operating room. A 78-year-old diabetic patient had fibular palsy of the nerve that healed after three months. In no case was thromboembolism observed. HHS is presented at different times in patients in [Table / Figure-2].

[table/Fig-2]: The Harris Hip Score in patients before and after total hip arthroplasty in the third, sixth, telfth and twenty-fourth weeks.		
time of Evaluation	harris hip Score	
	mean	low level-high level
Before Surgery	49.69±5.00	48.37-51
3 rd week	42.77±5.66	41.28-44.26
6 th week	70.36±6.05	68.76-71.95
12 th week	76.56±4.39	77.41-79.73
24 th week	88.02±4.04	87.05-89.18

As can be seen, mean HHS decreased during the first three weeks, but was later associated with an increase in amount over time. Mean pre-operative HHS was 49.69 ± 5.00 and increased to 88.02 ± 4.04 (p <0.001) after 24 weeks.

[table/Fig-3]: (a) Patient with disruptive osteoarthritis of right femoral head before total hip arthroplasty; (b) After six months, the femoral and acetabular components were stable.

[Table / Figure 3] shows a good result for the patient who first presented the destructive osteoarthritis of the right femoral head six months after surgery. The patient was able to walk well and without delay and was able to do all necessary routine work without pain or limitation.

We have tried at various times to examine the connection among HHS and RA diseases and diabetes mellitus. In this sense, there was no significant change in HHS among groups with and without these two diseases [Table / Figure 4,5].

[table/Fig-4]: Comparison of Harris Hip score between Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) patients and non-rheumatoid arthritis patients.

* Rheumatoid arthritis

time of Evaluation	harris hip Score		p-value
	ra* subjects (mean±SD)	Non-ra subjects (mean±SD)	
Before Surgery	47.87±2.29	49.98±5.27	0.27
3 rd week	41.62±3.11	42.96±5.97	0.35
6 th week	72.25±6.04	70.06±6.06	0.34
12 th week	79.62±4.98	78.40±4.32	0.46
24 th week	88.12±4.58	88.12±4.00	0.99

[table/Fig-5]: Comparison of Harris Hip score between diabetic patients and nondiabetic patients.

time of Evaluation	harris hip Score		p-value
	Diabetic subjects (mean±SD)	Non-diabetic subjects (mean±SD)	
Before Surgery	47.50±6.02	49.85±4.95	0.36
3 rd week	41.00±6.37	42.90±5.65	0.52
6 th week	70.00±2.16	70.38±6.25	0.9
12 th week	76.75±4.57	78.70±4.39	0.39
24 th week	84.50±5.91	88.38±3.81	0.06

DISCUSSION:

In this study, we assessed the results of patients undergoing THA. As noted, HHS cases increased from 49.7 preoperatively to 88 six months after THA, which showed a satisfactory result. Sachde B et al. He found that the average preoperative HHS in THA patients was 49.1 and reached 89.9 four years later, and the patients were completely satisfied with the operation. Gross AE et al. THA has also been claimed to improve patients' quality of life. In addition, a long-term study in 90% of elderly patients) shows that the long-term THA results in young patients are comparable to those in older patients. Sharma et al. Comparing the results of hemiarthroplasty and THA, the average HHS in the THA group was substantially higher than in the hemiarthroplasty group (90 to 80). These good results were also obtained in other studies showing that THA is beneficial for improving patient health⁸. In our study, there was no significant difference among RA and non-RA patients at different times in terms of average HHS. Schnaser EA et al.⁹ found that RA and other inflammatory diseases may affect recovery after surgery¹⁰. On the other hand, although RA patients had more comorbidities, postoperative complications were lower in RA patients than in patients with osteoarthritis. One study showed that RA patients with primary THA survived similarly to patients with osteoarthritis. Another study has shown that THA may be a good option for patients who are candidates for RA¹¹ surgery. These reports are consistent with our results and show that RA patients probably have no restrictions on THA. However, more research is needed to confirm this problem.

HHS in diabetic patients who underwent THA was not significantly higher than those without diabetes. In a previous study, HHS was not different between diabetic and non-diabetic patients, but the risk of infection may increase in diabetics¹². On the other hand, some researchers explained that the results of diabetes patients are controversial. This could be due to factors such as the duration of diabetes, how to manage it and other underlying diseases. Therefore, additional research is desired to determine the relationship among THA results and diabetes. In our study, post-operative complications included infection (1 case), neural damage (1 case) and posterior displacement (2 cases). In the study by Trojani C et al¹³. The most common postoperative complications were reported as deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism. In addition, Schairer WW et al¹⁴ documented that the complication rate changed at different times after surgery. They also stated that the infection mainly occurred in the first trimester. One of the complications is an infection that can cause many problems for the patient. Therefore, the surgeon and the patient should try to avoid the incidence of

surgical infection. In addition, all infections must be treated before surgery¹⁵. Another potential complication is the more common dislocation in patients undergoing fracture surgery and/or patients with pelvic muscle weakness. Differences in postoperative complications depend on many factors, such as surgical facilities, the skill and experience of the surgeon, the underlying diseases of the patient, adherence to health guidelines, etc.

LIMITATION

One of the limitations to be noted is that the working time is not long enough to investigate long-term complications after surgery. In addition, more studies with larger samples are recommended.

CONCLUSION:

THA had satisfactory results for osteoarthritis patients and the incidence of complications was insignificant. These findings support the fact that THA is a viable option for treatment.

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